

D4.1 Report on Training Activities of Public Procurers

April 2024

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Work Package	4
Delivery Date (DoA)	30.4.2024
Actual Delivery Date	30.4.2024

Document Revision History			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of Main Changes
25/4/2024	01.00	Anni Lahtela, Riikka Leskinen, Robert Miskuf	Initial version submitted to PEDAL
30/4/2024	02.00	Anni Lahtela	Final version

Dissemination Level and Nature of the Deliverable		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Nature	R = Report, E = Ethics or, O = Other	R

BUILD Consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PEDAL	SK
2	CIVITTA EESTI AS	CE	EE
3	CITY OF TURKU	Turku	FI
4	VARSINAIS-SUOMENLIITTO	Valonia	FI
5	TARTU LINN	Tartu	EE
6	GEMEENTE ROTTERDAM	ROTTERDAM	NL

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BUILD

Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities

Grant Agreement: 101070745

Funding Scheme: HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions (CSA)

Theme: HORIZON-EIE-2021-CONNECT-01-02

Start Date of Project: 01 October 2022

Duration: 24 months

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1 Objective of the WP and task

This task addressed the following specific objectives of the project:

- Encouraging cooperation and knowledge sharing between public buyers to promote the use of public procurement to contribute to the development of sustainable innovation, thus creating a fertile platform for future collaboration.
- Facilitating the enhancement of innovation knowledge and skills within buyers, raising awareness about co-design process between SMEs and buyers that may help to discover the most up-to-date innovative technological solutions, and assist in their development and further acquisition

The aim of WP 4 is to increase the capacities of public buyers to implement PPIs. Task 4.1 is about organising four international trainings for public buyers and one English webinar for international audience. Valonia was responsible for the coordination of this task. Core things that the BUILD consortium wanted to address through these trainings were:

- How to identify the potential of innovations
- How other cities have approached innovative procurements
- What are the different ways to reach an innovative goal
- How can innovative procurement be used to achieve new goals that address the challenges of our time
- What kinds of experiences have cities gained from different procurement methods

2 Planning

Planning of the task started in the fall of 2023. The consortium concluded that organizing half-day country-specific training sessions was the best approach. It was seen that half-day events had the greatest potential for attracting participants. Discussions on the format of the training sessions, webinar (see section 4), practical arrangements, and schedules took place in several monthly meetings in the autumn of 2023.

2.1 Target groups

Among the project implementers, it was decided that the training sessions were directed to procurement specialists and public buyers motivated to procure innovations and seeking best practices and useful tools in procurement. In other words, the training sessions were not aimed at or targeted towards individuals who were not familiar with innovative procurement practices. With this targeting, the training time could be used efficiently, and most of the time could be dedicated to concrete case examples rather than background theory.

2.2 Collecting of the cases

The consortium decided, based on the proposal from Valonia and the City of Turku, to establish the training structure based on case examples. Valonia provided the other project partners with a

template with the headings and questions through which the case examples would be addressed. Each country was requested to provide two good examples of innovative procurements, which would be compiled as a basis for the international webinar and utilized as examples in the training sessions held in each project country.

Care was taken to ensure that the following topic areas were covered in the examples:

- Guiding Principles
- Legal Knowledge and Procedures
- Preliminary market consultation
- Pre-commercial procurement
- Competitive dialogue
- Competitive procedure with negotiation
- Innovation partnership
- Legal questions and considerations
- Risk assessment

Partners provided the necessary cases. The whole consortium went through the cases as a peer learning process in an inner workshop held in February. The workshop enabled deeper understanding on the findings and learnings from the case examples.

3 General Communication

The communication of the training session was a coordinated and shared effort among all BUILD partners. Valonia first drafted a marketing pitch document, displaying the major information about the training sessions time and date, their topic focus and goals. This document was then used by PEDAL to produce a communication kit, available as a shared document on Google Docs, where all partners could comment and be updated about the latest advancements. This strategy proved to be efficient to deal with the dates changes and to facilitate feedback collection. The marketing pitch was free to be edited and used freely by any other BUILD partner.

The webinar invite and promotion were carried out through the BUILD communication channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, X), the BUILD email and through Partners' social media channels. The national training sessions were promoted via BUILD Social Media channels, while the registration and continuous communication was managed individually by each national partner, as the communication happened in their respective language. The email communication built upon the T3.3 Engagement and Onboarding, which collected a list of contacts interested in Innovation Procurement training and in following the BUILD activities. GDPR sensitive contacts were reached individually by each responsible BUILD partner, while the rest was reached directly via the BUILD project email, activity carried out by PEDAL.

The promotion of the training sessions was also supported by the Innovation Procurement Task Force partners, who reposted the Social Media post to increase their outreach among their audience.

PEDAL drafted a communication plan both for the webinar training session and for the national training, as a suggestion on the coordinated launching days. Each partner promoted the national training session according to their communication calendar and they were free to adapt and translate

the suggested text, at their best convenience. Some participants were directly contacted via email or via private means, as part of the partners' professional network.

PEDAL prepared the Registration Form which was linked to all the Social Media Posts, emails and the article. The contacts collected were then further contacted with 5 emails, where the first four acted as reminders, and the last one was a follow-up email to share further information on the national training as well as sharing the presentation shared during the webinar.

Different banners were made by PEDAL to promote all the training sessions. The BUILD partners were responsible for translating the text of the banner into their national language. The banners made are listed below:

Figure 1 - Webinar banners

Figure 2 - General information on National Training banner

Figure 3 - Finland national training banner

Training innovatieve inkoop methodes

Funded by the European Union

Datum: Vrijdag 12 april van 9:00 tot 12:00 uur
Locatie: Timmerhuis (halvemaanpassage 1) in Rotterdam. Ruimte 5.023
Sprekers: onder meer Leyla Bozkurt (advocaat aanbestedingsrecht) en Godard Croon (trainer circulair inkopen)
Kosten: gratis

Let op: er zijn slechts een beperkt aantal plaatsen beschikbaar, dus meld je zo spoedig mogelijk aan via dit emailadres: nam.koendjibiharie1@rotterdam.nl

BUILD Gemeente Rotterdam

Figure 4 - Netherlands national training banner

Innovatiivsete hankemeetodite alane koolitus

Funded by the European Union

Aeg
3. aprill 2024 kell 13.00-16.00

Koht
VSpa, Soome saal, Riia 2, Tartu ja
Online via Teams

Registreerimine
Kasutage kirjelduses olevat linki.
Tähtaeg: kohapeal on 27. märts, internetis 1. aprill

Maksumus
Tasuta

TARTU **BUILD** **civitta**

Figure 5 - Estonia national training banner

Figure 6 - Slovakia national training banner

4 Webinar

The webinar targeted at an international audience was also built on the collected case examples. The duration of the webinar was set to one hour, as it was thought to be challenging to engage participants for a longer period. The webinar took place on March 6th, 2024. The program of the webinar looked as follows:

- Introduction: Is procuring innovations difficult and risky?
Riikka Leskinen, Valonia
 - Case 1: Customer Guidance Service – Pilot Procurement based on outcome
Hedy Meinander, Procurement Services, City of Turku
 - Case 2: MaaS (Mobility as a Service) solution - Competitive dialogue
Jaanus Tamm, Project Manager, Tartu City Government
 - Case 3: Zero emission vehicle – Negotiation procedure
Simon De Roo, Expert buyer, Municipality of Rotterdam
 - Conclusions: Market dialogue & know your risks
Riikka Leskinen, Valonia
- Marketing pitch for the upcoming national trainings

The final number of participants in the webinar was 47.

The webinar was recorded and is available for viewing on YouTube¹.

¹ <https://youtu.be/EY759zLpmdU?si=Z7naR-UIM5phdryl>

5 Trainings in different countries

Valonia drafted a reporting template for all the partners to use to report their training experiences. It was an efficient way to collect all the necessary reporting information.

5.1 Finland

5.1.1 General information

The training was held as a hybrid event, both in the premises of the City of Turku in downtown Turku and via Teams, on Wednesday, March 27th, 2024, from 9:00 AM to 12:00 PM. In total, nearly 60 participants attended the event, with 14 present in person and 43 participating remotely.

5.1.2 Agenda and speakers

Agenda included five case examples of innovative public procurements. Two cases were from Turku, one from Tartu, one from Rotterdam and one from Slovakia. Every case had a different focus:

- Focus on identifying the challenge
- Focus on defining the market situation
- Focus on method selection
- Focus on risk management and sharing and
- Focus on the procurement's impact on the operating environment and markets.

Ville Valovirta, Senior Scientist at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland gave comments on every case and shared recent studies about the topics that were focused on in each case. To make sure that discussion between procurement units arises during the training, questions were sent beforehand to three different cities who participated in the training. The questions were following:

- How does the needs assessment for procurements start for you? Do you have a good practice or do you go with the situation? Is there a specific division of work or a way to gather insights from staff, customers, or stakeholders?
 - City of Turku answered this question with case examples.
- What are your most successful practices for market dialogue? Do you have an example of a particularly successful market survey/dialogue?
 - City of Kerava (Noora Harju-Saarinen) and Joensuu (Tuomas Vepsä) answered this question with case examples.
- What experiences/examples do you have of successfully procuring genuinely new, functional solutions or operating models that have generated broader demand?
 - City of Oulu (Helena Ylisirniö) answered this question with one case example.

Speakers of the day were the following:

- Riikka Leskinen Director at Valonia
- Susanna Sarvanto-Hohtari Procurement Director at city of Turku
- Ville Valovirta Senior Scientist at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland

- Simon de Roo Procurement specialist at Rotterdam city
- Hedy Meinander project coordinator at city of Turku

5.1.3 Marketing and communication

The training was marketed via:

- Valonia's LinkedIn
- Turkus Procurement Services LinkedIn
- newsletter from Keino (Competence Center for Sustainable and Innovative Public Procurement)
- the directors for the biggest procurement units in Finland
- own contacts in other cities procurement units, to the city organization in Turku
- a Teams group for innovative public procurements in Finland
- Valonia's website and newsletter

Sign up for the training and communication to participants was handled through Lytyi-service.

5.1.4 Overall review and observations

The topics and issues that sparked discussion during the training were the importance of market dialogues, outcome based procurement methods and how to impact on the operating environment and markets via public procurement.

The training generated interest among many participants. It didn't take much marketing effort to get 60 participants to join. The training was meant for procurement specialists from all of the procurement units in Finland, which made it attractive to procurement specialists throughout the country. We had participants from over 10 different procurement units in Finland. Valonia sent a feedback survey to the participants, and the results were good. All the feedback was positive and the participants said that the training was worth their time and effort, that the topics were good and interesting and done in a way that kept the listener interested through the whole training, and that they wish to have similar trainings in the future as well, with real life case examples.

Figure 7 - Riiikka Leskinen speaking about Mobility as a Service procurement

5.2 Tartu

5.2.1 General information

The training was held in person at VSpa Conference Center, Riia 2, Tartu; and simultaneously via Teams April 3, 2024, 13.00-16.00. Overall 47 participants, 15 on site.

5.2.2 Agenda and speakers

The programme of the training was as follows:

- 13:00 – 13:10 | Opening words
- 13:10 – 13:40 | Present on Dutch Public Procurement and steps of needs assessment (in English) Henk Jan Siersema, PIANOo, senior advisor, Expertisecentrum Aanbesteden
- 13:40 – 14:10 | Pre-procurement technical dialogue - a source of procurers' fears and opportunities for innovation procurement (in Estonian) Rahel Klaas, lawyer/senior consultant, CIVITTA Eesti AS
- 14:10 – 14:30 | The use of competitive dialogue in procurement (in Estonian) Jaanus Tamm, project manager, Tartu City Government
- 14.30 – 14.40 | Introduction to the online innovation procurement guide (in Estonian) Siret Suurväli, procurement lawyer, Estonian Business and Innovation Agency
- 14:40 – 15:10 | Coffee break
- 15:10 – 16:00 | Moderated discussion (in Estonian) Liina Helstein, Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Head of Tartu office

5.2.3 Marketing and communication

The training was marketed directly via email invitation to Tartu City Government employees dealing with procurements, to Tartu County employees, to the members of Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, and to CIVITTA mailing list. Also participated in LinkedIn training communication. We conveyed through discussions with City employees, CIVITTA and Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Industry the potential participants. Also previous experiences with procurement training was taken into consideration.

5.2.4 Overall review and observation

The participants were very much interested in the presented topics, especially the legal aspects. It was moderately easy to attract participants.

The topics and issues that sparked discussion during the training were numerous. The lack of resources (in English and Estonian) to check if your procurement is innovative; from what point are we talking about innovation; the issue of Estonia and hence budgets being small - e.g. we do not have dedicated people in City Government to deal only with procuring; how to recognize an innovative procurement / to procure something innovatively; how to change the mindset that a unsuccessful procurement is a shame; how to manage the budget and timeline of a innovative procurement.

Some key observations from the organizers and participants:

- This is a very niche problem for plenty of public procurers
- The lack of shared resources is felt strongly

- Participants had a very high interest in the soon published online innovation procurement guide

Figure 8 - Tartu training session hall

5.3 Rotterdam

5.3.1 General information

The training took place in person at Het Timmerhuis, a location in the centre of Rotterdam on Friday, April 12th, 2024, from 9.00 AM to 13:00 PM. In total around 45 participants attended from the cities of Rotterdam, Utrecht, Den Haag, Hogeschool Rotterdam and Dienst Justitiële Inrichtingen.

5.3.2 Agenda and speakers

Programme of the training was as follows:

- 9:00-9:20 | Introduction and explanation of the BUILD project
- 9:20 -10:05 | Explanation of the different innovative public procurement procedures, with focus on the legal possibilities. Including interaction.
Speaker: Leyla Bozkurt, lawyer public procurement law
Break – 5 minutes
- 10:10-10:55 | Explanation sustainable procurement and how to reach. With statements to discuss.

Speaker: Godart Croon, trainer and coach HowToChange

Break – 10 minutes

- 11:05-11:50 | Discussion in small groups about statements/questions innovative procedures
- 11:50-12:00 | Conclusions
- 12:00-13:00 | Lunch and networks.

5.3.3 Marketing and communication

The training was marketed directly via email invitation to employees of the city of Rotterdam dealing with procurements. Also we sent email invitations to our contacts at the cities of Utrecht, Den Haag and Amsterdam. We also used the G4 (4 big cities of the Netherlands: Den Haag, Utrecht, Rotterdam and Amsterdam) LinkedIn for that matter. Besides that we communicated our contacts that would be interested to attend the training, like contacts at Hogeschool Rotterdam, Dienst Justitiële Inrichtingen and Port of Rotterdam. In our communication we used the Netherlands national training banner (see chapter 3). During the training we displayed several printed BUILD posters.

5.3.4 Overall review and observation

The participants were very much interested in the presented topics. There was a lot of interaction between the trainers and the participants.

Some key observations from the organizers and participants:

- There are plenty possibilities for innovative procedures that we can use more to reach innovative goals, like the Competitive procedure with negotiation, the Competitive dialogue and the Innovation Partnership;
- During this procedures you can get 'a break' to consult the market and/or have dialogues with the markets. Goal: finding and or making concrete innovative solutions together;
- Use different aspects to reach innovative goals: the award criteria, requirements, requirements tenderers.

Figure 9 - Rotterdam training session hall

5.4 Slovakia

5.4.1 General information

The training was held at the Energy Management International Conference 2024², held at the Grand Hotel Bellevue in Slovakia, 8th - 9th April of 2024. The trainings took place during the parallel sessions organised during the event. The first took place from 13.00 to 15:00, the second training, held on the second day, took place from 11:00 to 13:00. Trainings had 119 participants, it was only an onsite event.

5.4.2 Agenda and speakers

Speakers

The BUILD expert speakers were Mr V. Oros and Mr. Juraj Revický to ensure a training tailored to the specific needs and background on Innovation Procurement present in Slovakia.

1. First day training Agenda on “Efficient Public Procurement of Energy Efficient Solutions”

- Procurement as an environmental policy tool
- The Directive and public procurement
 - Main tasks of the Member States under the Directive in relation to public procurement Promote energy-efficient means of mobility.
- Public Procurement of energy efficient solutions under the current legislation
 - Conditions of participation: from whom I procure
 - Objective, business model, description of the subject matter of the contract: what I am procuring
 - Business model
 - Description of the subject of the contract or concession
 - Example: The subject-matter of the contract is defined by the project
 - Evaluation criterion
 - GPP criteria
 - Procurement procedure
 - Recommended procurement schemes
- Practical examples
- Barriers to the procurement of energy efficient solutions
- Conclusions

2. Second day training on “Innovative EPC procurement with consideration of life cycle costs”

- Introduction
- The concept of innovative procurement PCP and PPI as process innovation
- Challenges in procurement innovation - findings in the Build project
- Public procurement of innovation is a transforming tool for the EU and Member States : why it is so important

² https://www.sstp.sk/evt_file.php?file=2473

- Objectives of the BUILD project
- A proposal for practical innovative procurement using the EPC (LCA positive) concept with complementary sustainability elements
- Environmental protection, social balance, good governance
- Life cycle costs in energy efficient building retrofit and the EPC concept
- Circular economy principles in energy efficient building renovation
 - Circularity: the urgency of circular construction and biomaterials
 - From design to utilisation through learning in nature and the use of digital technologies: a glimpse into the near future
 - Advantages of using biological materials
 - Building biomaterials
 - Lifecycle of biomaterials in constructions - hemp
- Green EPC projects
- Possibility of additional 'green criteria' as part of the MEAT criteria in the EPC RFP - the way they are applied must confirm the fulfilment of the commitment and the comparability of the tenders

Figure 10 - BUILD training session hall at the Energy Management Conference

5.4.3 Marketing and communication

The promotion of the training was done through Social Media channels, including the LinkedIn, Facebook and X accounts both of BUILD and PEDAL Consulting, with the support of some of the Innovation Procurement Task Force partners, who reposted the information. Additionally, partners from Tatra Tender and SSTP promoted the training session through their personal Social Media channels. Since the training session was included in the Conference program, it was therefore promoted through its website. A total of two posters plus flyers and leaflets were printed and disseminated among the present participants.

Figure 11 - BUILD flyers and leaflet displayed

5.4.4 Overall review and observation

The training session effectively covered a range of topics, sparking lively discussions among participants. The two key areas discussed were : "Effective public procurement of energy-efficient solutions" and "Innovative EPC procurement with consideration of life cycle costs". Additionally, significant attention was drawn to discussions on "state (grant) financing of the decarbonisation of companies (and households)."

The organisation of the training was commendable, with evident preparation and attention to detail. The event's structure and content were well-received, evidenced by the high turnout of participants. Indeed, it wasn't difficult to gather a public of 119 stakeholders. The involvement of strong partners, coupled with a well-planned and attractive program, facilitated the ease of attracting participants.

6 Collective Learnings / Summary

The need for innovations rises especially when the conventional solution is no longer sufficient. At the same time. Also, the complex challenges the cities are facing through climate change and biodiversity loss, augmentation of prizes and societal challenges drive them to seek new solutions. However, there is an urgent need for procurement know-how.

The definition of innovative procurement is very stretchy so we can ask from what perspective are we talking about innovations? Innovative procurement is a new method or solution at least to the procuring organisation - sometimes even to the market. It takes a lot more time and cooperation within the procuring unit and with the market to succeed in innovative procurement.

These kind of peer trainings are important and it is essential to go deep into concrete case examples in order to learn how others have proceeded in their procurement. Cases also help us to understand what is considered an innovative procurement. One core question seems to be: How to recognize that an innovative procurement is needed? And furthermore: How to form the best possible process for the procurement? It is challenging to manage the budget, timeline and resources of an innovative process.

The webinar rose interest but the face-to-face trainings were those that brought peers together to discuss. The topics and issues that sparked discussion during the trainings were numerous. We hope that we can change the mindset that an unsuccessful procurement is a shame - at least it is a very useful learning process.

Through BUILD-trainings we experienced that it is easy to attract an interested audience when the content of the training is concrete and the structure is well prepared. Procurement experts in European cities are seeking learning and peer discussion and we need to put further effort in common capacity building and pointing out interesting case examples.

Table 1 - Total number of participants in webinar and trainings

Event	Participants
Webinar	47
Finland	58
Rotterdam	45
Tarto	47
Slovakia	119
TOTAL	316